

Algebraic Closure of Finite Fields

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March 27, 2025

Abstract

In this presentation, we will construct and prove the algebraic closure of finite fields. We shall also study its Galois group.

1 Introduction

A field is called a finite field if it contains only a finite number of elements.

Fix a prime $p \in \mathbb{Z}$, then the finite field (or Galois field) of order p^e , $e \geq 1$ would be denoted by $F(p^e)$. We know that $F(p^e)$ is the splitting field of the polynomial $x^{p^e} - x$ over \mathbb{Z}_p . In so doing we have that $F(p^e) \subset F(p^m)$ whenever $e \mid m$. In particular, we have an infinite chain as below:

$$F(p^{1!}) \subset F(p^{2!}) \subset F(p^{3!}) \subset \dots \subset F(p^{n!}) \subset \dots$$

Denote by

$$F(p^\infty) = \bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} F(p^{n!})$$

Theorem 1.1. Let q be a prime power. Then:

- (i). F_q is a subfield of F_{q^n} for every integer $n \geq 1$;
- (ii). The Galois group $\text{Aut}_{F_q} F_{q^n}$ is a cyclic group of order n with generator $\sigma : \alpha \mapsto \alpha^q$.
- (iii). F_{q^m} is a subfield of F_{q^n} if and only if m divides n .

Definition 1.2. A **directed set** is a nonempty partially ordered set I such that for all $i_1, i_2 \in I$, there is an element $j \in I$ for which $i_1 \leq j$ and $i_2 \leq j$.

Definition 1.3. An **inverse system** $\{G_i, \phi_{ij}\}$ of finite groups indexed by a directed set I consists of a family $\{G_i \mid i \in I\}$ of finite groups and a family of $\{\phi_{ij} \in \text{Hom}(G_j, G_i) \mid i, j \in I, i \leq j\}$ of maps such that ϕ_{ii} is the identity on G_i for each i and $\phi_{ij} \circ \phi_{jk} = \phi_{ik}$ whenever $i \leq j \leq k$. Recall that $\text{Hom}(G_j, G_i)$ denotes the set of group homomorphisms from G_j to G_i .

For an inverse system $\{G_i, \phi_{ij}\}$ of finite groups indexed by a directed set I , we form the Cartesian product $\prod_{i \in I} G_i$ viewed as a product group. We also consider the subset of $\prod_{i \in I} G_i$ given by

$$D := \{(x_i) \in \prod_{i \in I} G_i \mid \phi_{ij}(x_j) = x_i \text{ for all } i, j \in I \text{ with } i \leq j\}$$

Proposition 1.4. D forms a subgroup of $\prod_{i \in I} G_i$.

Proof. Omitted.

Definition 1.5. We call D the **inverse limit** of $\{G_i, \phi_{ij}\}$, denoted by $\lim_{\leftarrow} G_i$.

Example 1.6. Define a partial order in the set \mathbb{N} of positive integers as follows: for $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$,

let $m \leq n$ if and only if $m \mid n$. For each positive integer i , let G_i be the cyclic group $\mathbb{Z}/i\mathbb{Z}$ and for each pair $(i, j) \in \mathbb{N}^2$ with $i \mid j$, define $\phi_{ij} : \bar{n} \in G_j \mapsto \bar{n} \in G_i$, with the bar indicating the formation of a residue class. Thus, it is easy to verify that the family $\{\mathbb{Z}/i\mathbb{Z}, \phi_{ij}\}$ forms an inverse system of finite groups indexed by \mathbb{N} . The inverse limit $\lim_{\leftarrow} \mathbb{Z}/i\mathbb{Z}$ is denoted by $\hat{\mathbb{Z}}$. This is also called the **profinite completion of the integers**.

Example 1.7. Let F_q be the finite field with q elements. We consider the family of Galois groups $G_i = \text{Aut}_{F_q} F_{q^i}$ for each $i \in \mathbb{N}$. we define a partial order in \mathbb{N} as in Example 1.5. above. For each pair $(i, j) \in \mathbb{N}^2$ with $i \mid j$, define the homomorphism $\phi_{ij} : \sigma_j \in G_j \mapsto \sigma_j|_{F(q^i)} \in G_i$ where $\sigma_j|_{F(q^i)}$ stands for the restriction of σ_j to F_{q^i} . Then $\{\text{Aut}_{F_q} F_{q^i}, \phi_{ij}\}$ forms an inverse system of finite groups indexed by \mathbb{N} .

Proposition 1.8. The profinite completion of the integers is isomorphic to the product of the **p-adic integers** for all prime number p . i.e.

$$\hat{\mathbb{Z}} \cong \prod_{p \text{ prime}} \mathbb{Z}_{(p)}$$

Proof. Omitted.

2 main Results

2.1 Algebraic Closure.

Theorem 2.1.1. $F(p^\infty)$ is an algebraically closed field with characteristic p . Furthermore, $F(p^e)$ is contained in $F(p^\infty)$ for all $e \geq 1$. Finally, $F(p^\infty)$ is the algebraic closure of $F(p^e)$ for all $e \geq 1$.

Proof. Let $x, y \in F(p^\infty)$ then there exists some n such that $x, y \in F(p^{n!})$. So $x + y$ and xy are contained in $F(p^{n!})$ and also in $F(p^\infty)$. The properties of a field are thus inherited and we have that $F(p^\infty)$ is a field. Furthermore, for any $e \geq 1$, $F(p^e)$ is contained in $F(p^{e!})$ as $e \mid e!$, and so $F(p^e)$ is contained in $F(p^\infty)$. Now, given any polynomial $p(x)$ over $F(p^\infty)$ then there exists some n such that $p(x)$ is a polynomial over $F(p^{n!})$. As the splitting field of $p(x)$ is a finite extension of $F(p^{n!})$, so it is a finite field $F(p^e)$ for some e , and hence contained in $F(p^\infty)$. Therefore, $F(p^\infty)$ is algebraically closed. Also, by definition of algebraic closure (Hungerford Theorem 5.3.4), we have that $F(p^\infty)$ is an algebraic closure. The proof is complete.

Corollary 2.1.2. The algebraic closure of a finite field is countable.

Proof. By the construction above, the algebraic closure is a countable union of finite sets, so it is countable. The proof is complete.

We say that $F(p^\infty)$ is the algebraic closure up to field isomorphisms, there is only one algebraic closure of a field. The actual objects and constructions may vary. We shall give another construction for the algebraic closure below and we can also write a proof that is independent of Theorem 2.1.1.

Theorem 2.1.3. Let p be the characteristic of the field $F(q)$. Then to see that the algebraic closure of \bar{F}_q is the same as \bar{F}_p . Also the algebraic closure of $F(q)$ is given by

$$\bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} F(q^n)$$

Proof. Denote $U := \bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} F(q^n)$. It is clear that U is a subset of \bar{F}_q since $F(q^n)$ is a subset of \bar{F}_q . It is also easy to verify that U forms a field. Let

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=0}^s \lambda_i x^i$$

be a non-constant polynomial over U . Then, for $0 \leq i \leq s$ we have $\lambda_i \in F(q^{m_i})$ for some $m_i \geq 1$. Hence, $f(x)$ is a polynomial over $F(q^m)$, where $m = m_0 m_1 \dots m_s$. Let α be a root of $f(x)$. Then $F_{q^m}(\alpha)$ is an algebraic extension of $F(q^m)$ and $F_{q^m}(\alpha)$ is a finite-dimensional vector space over $F(q^m)$. Hence, $F_{q^m}(\alpha)$ is also a finite field containing $F(q)$. Let r be the degree of $F_{q^m}(\alpha)$ over $F(q^m)$. Then $F_{q^m}(\alpha)$ contains exactly q^{rm} elements, that is, $F_{q^m}(\alpha) = F(q^{rm})$. So α is an element of U . This shows that U is the algebraic closure \bar{F}_q . The proof is complete.

Corollary 2.1.4. The algebraic closure constructed in Theorem 2.1.1 and Theorem 2.1.3 are isomorphic.

Proof. Immediate.

2.2 The Galois Group $Aut_{F_q} \bar{F}_q$

We have the now see the Galois group of the algebraic closure over it's finite fields as follows.

Theorem 2.2.1. We have that $Aut_{F_q} \bar{F}_q \cong \lim_{\leftarrow} Aut_{F_q} F_{q^i}$

Proof. For each $i \in \mathbb{N}$, we have a homomorphism $Aut_{F_q} \bar{F}_q \rightarrow Aut_{F_q} F_{q^i}$ obtained by restriction. These together yield a homomorphism

$$\theta : Aut_{F_q} \bar{F}_q \longrightarrow \prod_{i \in \mathbb{N}} Aut_{F_q} F_{q^i}$$

. It is clear that the image of θ is contained in $\lim_{\leftarrow} Aut_{F_q} F_{q^i}$. We now show that θ is an isomorphism onto $\lim_{\leftarrow} Aut_{F_q} F_{q^i}$.

Let $\sigma \neq 1$ be in $Aut_{F_q} \bar{F}_q$, then there exists an element $x \in \bar{F}_q$ such that $\sigma(x) \neq x$. By Theorem 2.1.3, x belongs to F_{q^n} for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Now the image of $\sigma \in Aut_{F_q} \bar{F}_q$ maps x to $\sigma(x)$, and thus $\theta(\sigma)$ is not the identity. Hence, θ is injective.

Take (σ_i) in $\lim_{\leftarrow} Aut_{F_q} F_{q^i}$. If $x \in \bar{F}_q$ and we set $\sigma(x) = \sigma_i(x)$, where $x \in F_{q^i}$, then this is an unambiguous definition of a map $\sigma : \bar{F}_q \rightarrow \bar{F}_q$. It is easy to check that σ is an element of $Aut_{F_q} \bar{F}_q$. Since $\theta(\sigma) = (\sigma_i)$, $\lim_{\leftarrow} Aut_{F_q} F_{q^i}$ is the image of θ . The proof is complete.

Corollary 2.2.2. We have that $Aut_{F_q} \bar{F}_q \cong \hat{\mathbb{Z}} \cong \prod_{p \text{ prime}} \mathbb{Z}_{(p)}$.

Proof. For each $i \in \mathbb{N}$, we can identify the group $Aut_{F_q} F_{q^i}$ with $\mathbb{Z}/i\mathbb{Z}$ by Theorem 1.1.(ii). Under this identification, the family of homomorphisms in Example 1.7 coincides with that in Example 1.6. Thus, the desired result follows from Theorem 1.2.5. The proof is complete.

It is another direct consequence of Theorem 2.2.1 that the restrictions of all automorphisms in $Aut_{F_q} \bar{F}_q$ to F_{q^m} give all automorphisms in $Aut_{F_q} F_{q^m}$, that is, we obtain the following result.

Corollary 2.2.3. For every integer $m \geq 1$, we have

$$Aut_{F_q} F_{q^m} = \{ \sigma |_{F_{q^m}} : \sigma \in Aut_{F_q} \bar{F}_q \}$$

Proof. Omitted.

For each $i \in \mathbb{N}$, let $\pi_i \in Aut_{F_q} F_{q^i}$ be the automorphism $\pi_i : x \mapsto x^q$. Then the element (π_i) is in $\lim_{\leftarrow} Aut_{F_q} F_{q^i}$. This yields an automorphism in $Aut_{F_q} \bar{F}_q$. We call it the **Frobenius** automorphism of F_q over \bar{F}_q , denoted by π . It is clear that $\pi(x) = x^q$ for all $x \in \bar{F}_q$ and that the restriction of π to F_{q^i} is π_i , the Frobenius automorphism of F_q over F_{q^i} .

3 Other Applications

In this section, we will talk about other useful results and applications in a finite field.

Definition 3.1. Let $\alpha \in \bar{F}_q$ and $\sigma \in \text{Aut}_{F_q}\bar{F}_q$. The element $\sigma(\alpha)$ is called a **conjugate** of α with respect to F_q .

Lemma 3.2. The set of conjugates of an element $\alpha \in \bar{F}_q$ with respect to F_q is equal $\{\pi^i(\alpha) \mid i = 0, 1, 2, \dots\}$, where $\pi \in \bar{F}_q$ is the Frobenius automorphism.

Proof. Let $\sigma \in \text{Aut}_{F_q}\bar{F}_q$. There exists an integer $m \geq 1$ such that α is an element of F_{q^m} . Then the restrictions $\sigma|_{F_{q^m}}$ and $\pi|_{F_{q^m}}$ are both elements of $\text{Aut}_{F_q}F_{q^m}$. Moreover, $\pi|_{F_{q^m}}$ is a generator of $\text{Aut}_{F_q}F_{q^m}$. Thus, $\sigma|_{F_{q^m}} = (\pi|_{F_{q^m}})^i$ for some $i \geq 0$. Hence, $\sigma(\alpha) = \sigma|_{F_{q^m}}(\alpha) = (\pi|_{F_{q^m}})^i(\alpha) = \pi^i(\alpha)$. The proof is complete.

Proposition 3.3. All distinct conjugates of an element $\alpha \in \bar{F}_q$ with respect to F_q are $\alpha, \pi(\alpha), \dots, \pi^{m-1}(\alpha)$, where m is the least positive integer such that F_{q^m} contains α , that is, m is such that $F_{q^m} = F_q(\alpha)$.

proof. The restriction $\pi|_{F_{q^m}}$ of π to F_{q^m} has order m since it is a generator of $\text{Aut}_{F_q}F_{q^m}$. Hence, $\pi^m(\alpha) = (\pi|_{F_{q^m}})^m(\alpha) = \alpha$. This implies that $\alpha, \pi(\alpha), \dots, \pi^{m-1}(\alpha)$ yield all conjugates of α . It remains to show that they are pairwise distinct. Suppose that $\pi^n(\alpha) = \alpha$ for some $n \geq 1$. Then it is clear that $\pi^n(\beta) = \beta$ for all $\beta \in F_q(\alpha)$, that is, $\beta^{q^n} - \beta = 0$ for all elements $\beta \in F_{q^m}$. Thus, the polynomial $x^{q^n} - x$ has at least q^m roots. Hence, $n \geq m$. This implies that $\alpha, \pi(\alpha), \dots, \pi^{m-1}(\alpha)$ are pairwise distinct. The proof is complete.

Corollary 3.4. All distinct conjugates of an element $\alpha \in \bar{F}_q$ with respect to F_q are $\alpha, \alpha^q, \alpha^{q^2}, \dots, \alpha^{q^{m-1}}$, where m is the least positive integer such that F_{q^m} contains α , that is, m is such that $F_{q^m} = F_q(\alpha)$.

proof. This follows from Proposition 3.3 and also using the fact that $\pi(\alpha) = \alpha^q$.

References

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